

Synthesis of nano-sized metal oxide powders and their application in separation technology[†]

A. Pathak, A. B. Panda, A. Tarafdar and P. Pramanik*

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology Kharagpur, Kharagpur-721 302, India

E-mail : pramanik@chem.iitkgp.ernet.in Fax : 91-3222-55303

Manuscript received 19 September 2002

Nano-sized inorganic oxides that find application in various fields (such as, in catalysis, sensors, pigments, membranes etc.) are also reported to be excellent reagents in various separation technologies through selective adsorption. Depending on the chemistry of the constituent atoms, they are known to exhibit remarkable adsorption properties due to their enhanced surface area and large interface volume.

The nano-sized inorganic oxides can be produced by various reported physical and chemical methods. In general, the chemical methods offer the advantages of easy preparation of nearly any composition, maintaining compositional homogeneity and high purity. However, the chemical routes generally involve complex techniques and an improved level of skill is required to realize the benefits. We have been successful in standardizing the preparation of a variety of nano-sized inorganic oxides through thermolysis of a polymeric based aqueous precursor solution of the desired inorganic ions. The developed method is less cumbersome, more versatile, more cost effective and hence economically more viable than the existing ones for large-scale production of nano-sized inorganic oxides.

In this paper we present the preparation of nano-sized powders of Fe_3O_4 , Al_2O_3 and ZrO_2 . The obtained nano-sized oxide powders were sonicated in water and incorporated in the matrix of activated charcoal through adsorption. The oxide incorporated charcoal materials have been used as the adsorbing bed for the removal of trace amounts of fluoride/arsenite and arsenate ions from industrial wastewater and aldehyde from the perfume grade alcohols. The oxides have been prepared through thermolysis of precursor solutions that contained the respective cations homogeneously dispersed in the polymeric matrix of sucrose and polyvinyl alcohol. Calcination of the fluffy, carbonaceous precursor powder at 200–500°/2 h resulted in the desired inorganic oxide phase with particle diameters ranging between 20 and 38 nm and BET surface area ranging between 120 and 200 m^2/g . The charcoal embedded fine powders of the inorganic oxides have been able to remove fluoride/arsenite and arsenate ions from industrial wastewater upto 0.01–0.02 ppm levels.

Many of the perfume grade alcohols are produced by reduction of aldehyde by M.P.V. reduction using aluminum alkoxides or catalytic reduction using hydrogen. However, a ppm amount of residual aldehydes are perpetually retained in the alcohol even through the most efficient reduction by the mentioned process and changes the flavour of the perfume formulations. Here we report an efficient separation of cinnamaldehyde from cinnamyl alcohol using nano-sized Fe_3O_4 powders. For this, the adsorbing bed has been further modified by impregnating it with 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane in ethanol medium. The amino groups impregnated in the matrix readily undergoes reaction with the adsorbed aldehydes and results in the formation of Schiff bases thereby reducing the concentration of residual aldehyde contained in the alcohol to levels <0.2 ppm. The prepared adsorbent has been also tested for the removal of heptaldehyde from heptanol and octaldehyde from octanol. The major advantage of the process is that the adsorbent and the adsorbed aldehyde can be easily separated by applying an external magnetic field, thus avoiding the filtration process.

'Nanostructured materials' are amorphous/semicrystalline/crystalline¹ materials with crystallite/particle sizes (diameter ≤ 100 nm) in the submicrometer or nanometer scale. They exhibit properties much improved over those exhibited by conventional bulk materials (diameter >10 μm) because of their large surface-to-volume ratio. Among these nanostructured materials, the inorganic simple/mixed oxides form a

special class that have immense technological importance because of their use in catalysis/sensors/various separation technologies/electronic/magnetic/and other engineering materials. The performance of these products is primarily defined by the combination of their unique composition and their microstructures (which includes, size and morphology of the particles.) The microstructure mainly depends on the

[†]Dedicated to Professor R. P. Rastogi.

chemistry of its constitutional materials and on the way of its processing. And the preparations of various nanocrystalline inorganic oxide materials with uniform composition pose as a major challenge to the materials scientists for the improvement of existing materials and for the development of newer materials.

Applications of nano-sized inorganic oxide materials :

Nano-sized inorganic oxide materials are being increasingly used for newer and innovative applications in many area of technology² due to their crucial microstructure based properties. It has been recognized that specially tailored ultrafine microstructures permitted the generation of solids with new atomic and/or electronic structures, which lead to increased modified properties. For example, remarkable catalytic, electrical, magnetic, mechanical, and optical properties in nanostructured materials have been reported. A few of the particle size dependent properties of the nanocrystalline materials are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Summary of changes in properties in the nano-sized oxide materials

Catalytic :	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased catalytic activity due to enhanced surface area, large interface volume and modified coordination number of the surface atoms
Magnetic :	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase in magnetic coercivity down to a critical grain size • Below critical grain size, decrease in coercivity leading to super paramagnetic behavior
Electrical :	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Higher electrical conductivity in ceramics and magnetic nanocomposites • Higher electrical resistivity in metals
Mechanical :	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase in hardness and strength of metals and alloys • Enhanced ductility, toughness, toughness, and formability of ceramics
Optical :	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Blue-shift of optical spectra of quantum-confined crystallites • Increase in luminescence efficiency of semiconductors

The adjectives used to describe nanoparticulate materials include nanocrystalline, nanophase, nanosized and others. Nanoparticulate materials are also called nanoparticles, nanocrystals and nanopowders. Alternatively, the terminology 'zero-dimensional structures' has also been used to describe the result of this three-dimensional nanostructuring, that is, the restriction of the length, width and depth of a material from a finite (macroscopic) value to a virtually infinitesimal (nanoscopic) value. In certain electronic and optoelectric applications, nanoparticles are described as quantum dots in reference to the quantum mechanical confinement effects that result from their nanoscale dimensions³.

According to the pioneering work by Gleiter^{4,5} and other groups⁶⁻⁸, the properties of nanosized oxide materials are reported to be strongly governed by their surface structure and/or interface volume, which represent a significant fraction of their total volume. According to the model by Gleiter, the surface atoms in a nanocrystalline materials were reported to have (i) a lower density, (ii) a lower coordination number, (iii) a larger interatomic distance, (iv) and lower symmetry⁹. A modified coordination number of the surface atoms results in their modified electronic structure and related physical/chemical properties. Thus, a change of interface volume in small crystallites/particles, of size at a nano-meter scale, causes a significant change in their electronic structure, according to the chemistry of the constituent atoms. It is thus conceivable that many of the microstructure-based properties of fine-grained materials (such as, selective adsorption) differ from those of conventional bulk materials in which the interface volume fraction is negligible.

These physical properties, brought about by dimensional manipulation, have brought forth the vast application potentials for fine ceramic materials in a variety of fields. Some of the general functions, properties and applications of fine ceramics are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Current, emerging and future applications of nano-sized oxide materials

Biomedical/Pharmaceutical :

- Biological tagging
- Biomagnetic separations
- Diagnostic contrast agent
- Targeted drug delivery
- Mineral supplements
- Biomedical implants
- Sunscreens, UV protective cosmetics

Electronic/Magnetic/Optoelectronic :

- Optical fibers
- Optical modulators
- Photon detectors
- Photovoltaics-solar cells
- Photonic devices
- Superconductive wires
- Single electron transistor
- Laser diodes
- Passive electron devices
- Emitters for FEDs
- Advanced phosphor
- Industrial magnetic fluids
- Magnetic sound insulation
- Soft and hard magnets

Energy :

- Solid oxide fuel cell electrolyte
- Battery applications
- Propellants and explosive
- PEM fuel cell electrodes

Catalysis :

- Environmental catalyst
- Separation technology
- Water-gas shift catalyst
- Methanol synthesis/reform catalyst
- Photocatalytic air and water purification
- Toxic chemical clean-up
- Gas sensor
- Ceramic membranes

Table-2 (contd.)

Functional coatings :

- Water resistance coatings
- Flame retardant coatings
- UV protection coatings
- Smart window coating
- Transport colored coatings (automotive topcoats and wood stains)
- Antimicrobial coatings
- Scratch retardant coatings
- Electroconductive coatings
- Photocatalytic coatings

Structural/Abrasive/Other :

- Filler and reinforcements
- Precision abrasives (including CMP)
- IR transparent ceramic components
- Arc tubes of high intensity discharge lamps
- Ceramic armor
- Free-flow additives for powders
- Investment casting
- Cemented carbides

The growing applications of fine inorganic oxide materials have received interest in the multidisciplinary approach to their synthesis. The conventional method for processing of inorganic oxide materials through mechanical mixing of oxides or carbonates followed by calcination and ball milling though successful for a large-scale production of bulk powders because of its low cost and easy adaptability, has limitations¹⁰ in the production of fine powders. High temperatures and long heating schedules make the particles coarse and high-energy destruction (break down force)¹¹ is required to get the fine powders. Available literature from the last few decades^{5, 12} reveal that a lot of research activities have been focused on the development of new synthetic methods for the production of the fine inorganic oxide powders^{6-8, 13}.

The advanced ceramic materials are often tailor made to suit specific applications, and the chemical synthesis routes play a crucial role in their design and production. Fine powders prepared through chemical processes have better properties with an improved homogeneity. The chemical precursors used in the chemical processes can be easily refined to increase the purity and careful control of the solvent removal can lead to the production of crushable agglomerates. The synthesis of fine oxide powders by a chemical route are usually categorized under two broad headings of : (i) vapor phase reaction methods and (ii) solution processing methods.

Vapor phase reaction methods :

This process involves dissociation-vaporization of primary powders (reactants), followed by vigorous quenching of the resulting vapors on to a cold metal substrate. It results in a refined deposit of sample on substrate. Some of the widely used techniques for the production of fine inorganic oxide powders for device

applications include^{5, 15-17} : (i) inert gas condensation, (ii) sputtering, (iii) mechanical alloying, (iv) laser ablation, (v) spray conversion, (vi) plasma spraying, (vii) chemical vapor deposition.

Solution processing methods :

The 'Solution Processing Methods' are often considered to be synonymous to the 'Chemical Synthesis Methods'. This technique can be described to consist of an initial solution preparation step followed by solvent removal and then decomposition of the dried product to the respective final powders. In general, the solution processing methods offer the advantages of easy preparation of nearly any composition maintaining compositional homogeneity and high purity. The important solution based chemical synthesis methods popularly used for the preparation of fine-grained inorganic oxide powders, include : Solvent vaporization method, Precursor compound method, Aerosol method, Sol-gel method, Hydrothermal method, Other gel methods, Co-precipitation method, combustion method.

The various advantages and disadvantages of the discussed powder processing methods involved with the preparations of inorganic oxide powders are presented in Table 3.

Synthetic methods where high temperatures are involved facilitate the formation of agglomerates by forming solid bridges on particle contacts. Therefore, low temperature methods (i.e. the various soft chemical methods) are necessary for the synthesis of weakly agglomerated sub-micron oxide powders. However, the chemical routes generally involve complex techniques that generally require a high degree of sophistication and control and an improved level of skill to realize the desired characteristic properties in the powders¹⁸, especially for the multi-component systems. And a better knowledge and understanding of the reactions and the mechanism, taking place in a chemical process is essential for successful commercial exploration of the methods. Moreover, the economic aspects of a particular chemical synthesis process needs to be balanced against the possible improvement in the powder characteristics before it could be considered to be commercially viable.

It is a decade¹⁹⁻²³ since the authors have been involved with the development and improvement of aqueous solution based preparative methods that are technically simple, less cumbersome, more versatile and are also adaptable for large-scale preparation of nano-sized powders of various inorganic oxide systems. The focus of the development of the solution based preparative method has always been to choose the most appropriate, easily available laboratory chemical

Table 3. Categorization of inorganic oxide powder processing methods

Preparation methods	Advantages	Disadvantages
Solid-state method :	Inexpensive, wide applicability	Limited purity, Limited homogeneity, Large particulates
Vapor phase methods :	High purity, very small particles, low agglomeration, good for non-oxides	Expensive, difficult for multicomponent systems
Solution processing techniques :	High purity, small particles with controlled composition, chemical homogeneity	Moderately expensive, agglomeration of particles, poor for non-oxides
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Solvent vaporization method • Hydrothermal method • Co-precipitation method • Sol-gel method • Precursor compound method • Combustion method 		

reagents that would result in the finest powders of the desired mixed system at the lowest heat-treatment temperatures with the best particle size distribution. And on the basis of the choice of the chemical reagents, used to compose the precursor solution, the preparative method has been termed as the 'Polymer-based precursor solution method'. The method involve thermolysis of a polymeric based aqueous precursor solution of the desired ions. The polymeric reagent used was an aqueous solution mixture of sucrose and polyvinyl alcohol (PVA). The fluffy, carbonaceous precursor powders produced on the thermolysis were calcined at 300–500° for 2 h to obtain the nano-sized powders of the desired oxide system.

Results and discussion

Thermal studies (simultaneously recorded DTA and TG) of the precursors of ZrO_2 , Fe_3O_4 and Al_2O_3 were carried out in air using thermal analyzer (Shimadzu DT-40) at a heating rate of $10^\circ \text{ min}^{-1}$, for determining the calcination

Fig. 1. DTA-TG diagram of the ZrO_2 precursor mass after drying over water bath; the data obtained with the heating at $5^\circ/\text{min}$.

temperature required for obtaining the final carbon-free pure oxide system (Fig. 1).

The precursors as well as the nano-sized powders of ZrO_2 , Fe_3O_4 and Al_2O_3 were characterized by room temperature X-ray powder diffraction studies using a Philips

diffractometer (PW 1710 and PW 1810) with CuK_α radiation. The studies confirmed the formation of the pure phase of the respective oxide system while the crystallite size were calculated by the X-ray line broadening studies using the Scherrers' equation²⁴.

The average particle diameters of the calcined oxide powders were measured using a transmission electron microscope (Philips TM300). The bright field TEM micrographs reflect the basic powder morphology where the smallest visible isolated spot can be identified with the particle/crystallite agglomerate (Figs. 2 and 3). The corresponding selected area electron diffraction (SAED) patterns showed rings patterns signifying the presence of an assembly of nano-crystallites (Fig. 2b).

The BET surface area measurements of the precursors of the prepared oxide powders were carried out by adorption of nitrogen gas at liquid nitrogen temperatures using Micromeritics high-speed surface area analyzer and were observed to range $120\text{--}200 \text{ m}^2\text{gm}^{-1}$.

The results of the above characterization are summarized in Table 4.

The method developed for the preparation of nano-sized oxides :

The general idea of the polymeric based precursor solution approach was to distribute the metal ions throughout the viscous polymeric matrix so that the complete evaporation of the precursor solution generated *in situ* a polar porous carbonaceous materials enriched with oxygen atoms that favored the accommodation of the metal ions in its matrix. Stability of the polymeric approach comes from the chemical bonding of the cations onto the polymeric chain and from the development of extremely high viscosity polymeric solution that favors low cation mobility in the completely evaporated precursor solution, which inhibits the crystallite agglomeration in the final product.

Fig. 2. (a) Bright field TEM micrograph and (b) the corresponding SAED pattern of Al_2O_3 powders.

Table 4. Summary of the characterization studies of the various metal oxides powders prepared through the polymer based precursor solution method

Sample	Sucrose ^a mol	Virgin precursor		Temp. ^b °C	Temp. ^d °C	Crystallite size ^e (± 2 nm)	Particle size ^f (± 5 nm)
		X-Ray phase	Surface area $\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$				
Fe_3O_4	0.04	Crystalline	120	~200 ^c	300/2 h	10	38
ZrO_2 (cubic)	0.04	Crystalline	160	~200 ^c	400/2 h	7	30
$\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$	0.04	Amorphous	200	400/2 h	500/2 h	20	21

^aSucrose solution containing 10-mole% of vinyl alcohol monomer units.

^bMinimum temperature required for the formation of the metal oxide phase.

^cHeat-treatment temperature of ~200° signifies the hot plate temperature during complete evaporation of the precursor solution

^dMinimum temperature required for obtaining the carbon free nano-sized metal oxide powders.

^eAverage value of the crystallite sizes calculated using the Scherrers' formula applied to the various d_{hkl} line of the oxide powders.

^fAverage diameters of the smallest visible isolated particle/crystallite agglomerate as observed from TEM for the oxide powders.

The PVA in the aqueous solution mixture of sucrose-PVA, when added to the precursor solutions, was likely to undergo a polycondensation reaction with the oxidized sucrose during the evaporation process. During the reaction the sucrose possibly gets tagged on to the PVA backbone as the pendant group resulting in a highly branched polymeric network structure. The metal ions possibly get held in the generated hydroxylic pockets of the branched-chain polymer

through chelation and ensure their atomistical dispersion throughout the created polymeric network structure.

Decomposition of the metal nitrates, along with sucrose and PVA, begins during the evaporation process and eventually culminates in a fluffy, carbonaceous precursor mass on complete evaporation. Pyrolysis of the precursor mass culminated in a polar porous carbonaceous precursor material enriched with oxygen atoms, while the metal ions formed clusters with the oxide ions and remained uniformly distributed in this resulting matrix of the porous carbon. The slow oxidation of the residual carbon in the precursors during calcination, aided by the catalytic effect of the *in situ* metal ions, released various gases from the pockets and made the structure highly porous and fluffy and favored the formation of nanocrystals of the respective oxides at relatively lower calcination temperatures. Thus, the carbonaceous materials generated from the complete evaporation of the polymeric reagent provided heat through combustion and facilitated the formation of the desired oxide phase at relatively lower calcination temperatures compared to the same oxide system when prepared through the other chemical routes reported so far.

Fig. 3. Bright field TEM micrograph of ZrO_2 powders.

Thus, the overall chemical reaction taking place in the formation of nano-sized metal oxide powders through the polymeric based aqueous precursor solution route can be represented by the chemical reactions as shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

The developed adsorbing bed :

Nano-sized inorganic oxides are reported to be excellent reagents in various separation technologies through selective adsorption. Depending on the chemistry of the constituent atoms, they are known to exhibit remarkable adsorption properties due to their enhanced surface area and large interface volume.

The nano-sized metal oxides containing multivalent metal ions (having valency more than 2) such as Fe₃O₄, Al₂O₃, and ZrO₂ are particularly proficient in removal of fluoride/arsenate/arsenite ions from industrial wastewater as well for the removal of trace amounts of aldehydes from their respective alcohols. The use of the metal oxide alone is not suitable due to their tendency to form colloids. Thus in this present study, the nano-sized metal oxides have been incorporated in the matrix of activated charcoal which prevents the leaching of the colloid particles due to its strong adsorption properties. Using the charcoal embedded fine powders of the inorganic oxides we have been able to remove fluoride/arsenite and arsenate ions from industrial wastewater upto 0.01–0.02 ppm levels while their concentration in the

untreated wastewater sample was >1000 ppm.

Many of the perfume grade alcohols are produced by reduction of aldehyde by M.P.V.^{25,26} reduction using aluminum alkoxides or catalytic reduction using hydrogen.

However, a ppm amount of residual aldehydes are perpetually retained in the alcohol even through the most efficient reduction by the mentioned process and changes the flavour of the perfume formulations. However, we in our study observed that when the adsorbing bed was prepared from charcoal embedded with nano-sized Fe₃O₄ and was impregnated with 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane in ethanol medium, then the concentration of residual aldehyde retained in the alcohol was not detectable upto 0.2 ppm while their concentration in the untreated sample of the alcohol was <1000 ppm. The amino groups impregnated in the matrix readily undergoes reaction with the adsorbed aldehydes and results in the formation of Schiff bases thereby reducing the concentration of residual aldehyde contained in the alcohol.

The overall process of the removal of cinnamaldehyde from a commercial grade sample of cinnamyl alcohol using the prepared magnetic adsorbing bed can be summarized by the chemical reactions presented in Scheme 2.

Moreover, since Fe₃O₄ is a magnetic material, hence applying an external magnetic field could easily separate the adsorbent and the adsorbed aldehyde thus the filtration

Scheme 2

process could be avoided.

Conclusion :

Nano-sized powders of Fe_3O_4 , ZrO_2 and Al_2O_3 have been prepared starting from a polymer-based aqueous precursor solution of the respective metal ions. The polymeric reagent of the aqueous solution mixture of sucrose and PVA provided the matrix for atomistic dispersion of the metal ions in the precursor solution. Thermolysis of the precursor solution culminated in a polar porous carbonaceous precursor material enriched with oxygen atoms, while the metal ions formed clusters with the oxide ions and remained uniformly distributed in this resulting matrix of the porous carbon. The slow oxidation of the residual carbon in the precursors during calcination, aided by the catalytic effect of the *in situ* metal ions, released various gases from the pockets and made the structure highly porous and favored the formation of nanocrystals of the respective oxides at relatively lower calcination temperatures (200–500°). The average particle size and the responding BET surface area of the prepared nano-sized powders of Fe_3O_4 , ZrO_2 and Al_2O_3 were found in the range 20–40 nm and 120-200 m^2g^{-1} respectively.

The adsorption bed, prepared embedding the nano-sized powders of Fe_3O_4 , ZrO_2 and Al_2O_3 in activated charcoal through adsorption have been found to have the ability to remove fluoride/arsenite and arsenate ions from industrial wastewater upto 0.01–0.02 ppm levels where their concentration in the untreated wastewater sample was >1000 ppm. The adsorption bed, prepared by impregnated the activated charcoal embedded with nano-sized Fe_3O_4 slurry with 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane in ethanol medium, was found drastically reduce the concentration of residual aldehyde retained in the alcohol upto 0.2 ppm while their concentration in the untreated sample of the alcohol was <1000 ppm.

In conclusion, the methodology developed for preparation of an adsorbing bed using nano-sized oxides of Fe_3O_4 , ZrO_2 and Al_2O_3 is an effective method for the separation of trace amounts of fluoride/arsenite and arsenate ions from industrial wastewater and aldehyde from the perfume grade alcohols. The process is technically simple, and uses easily available laboratory reagents, hence may be suitable for low cost manufacturing of high quality, nanocrystalline ceramic oxides separators.

Experimental

Preparation of the precursor solution for nano-sized ZrO_2 , Fe_3O_4 and Al_2O_3 powders : ZrO_2 was prepared

starting from an aqueous solution of zirconyl nitrate. To start with, an aqueous solution of zirconium oxychloride (~3 M) was prepared and then 35% NH_4OH solution was added to it in the molar ratio of 1 : 4. A white gelatinous precipitate of hydrous zirconyl hydroxide was obtained, which was filtered and washed with deionized water to completely remove the chloride ion and the excess ammonia. The precipitate was then dissolved in minimum quantity of HNO_3 to form the zirconyl nitrate solution having pH ~2 and was put to heat over a hot plate (at ~80°). Aqueous solution mixture of sucrose (4 moles per unit mole of the metal ion) and PVA (10 mole percent w.r.t. the total moles of the cation) was then added to the solution of zirconyl nitrate under hot condition (~80°) with constant stirring to compose the homogeneous, polymeric matrix based precursor solution.

Similarly, of appropriate stoichiometries of ferric nitrate and aluminum nitrate were taken and dissolved in deionized water and dispersed in the polymeric reagent of sucrose and PVA under hot condition to obtain the homogeneous polymeric matrix based precursor solution of the respective oxide system.

Each of the precursor solutions was then separately evaporated to dryness and subsequently pyrolyzed to obtain the fluffy, carbonaceous precursor powders of the respective oxides. These precursors were then calcined for the removal of the residual carbon and for the formation of the nano-sized particulates of the pure oxide phase.

Removal of fluoride/arsenite and arsenate ions from water : Appropriate amounts of the prepared nano-sized powders of ZrO_2 , Fe_3O_4 and Al_2O_3 were separately taken and sonicated in aqueous medium to obtain a colloidal suspension. Predetermined amount of activated charcoal were then soaked in the colloidal suspensions of the respective oxide system with the pH of the system maintained at 7. The amount of the activated charcoal used was maintained around 15% (w/w) with respect to the total amounts of the respective oxides. The fine powders of the oxides got incorporated in the matrix of the activated charcoal through adsorption. The black slurry was finally dried (at 120°) to obtain the adsorbing bed for the removal of trace amounts (ppm level) of fluoride/arsenite and arsenate ions from industrial wastewater.

For analysis, the concentrations of F^- ions in aliquot of the industrial wastewater were checked-through complexometric titration-using zirconium salt and the concentrations of $\text{AsO}_3^{3-}/\text{AsO}_4^{3-}$ ions were checked using Marsch test. Thereafter, the charcoal embedded with oxide was stirred with aliquot amounts of the same water sample for 0.5 h. The suspension was filtered and the filtrate was subsequently

checked for the concentration of the $F^-/AsO_3^{3-}/AsO_4^{3-}$ ions.

Removal of aldehydes from their respective alcohols : For separation of cinnamaldehyde from cinnamyl alcohol, the adsorbing bed was prepared by embedding nano-sized Fe_3O_4 powders in the matrix of the activated charcoal by the method mentioned above. This magnetic adsorbing bed was further modified by impregnating it with 3-aminopropyl-triethoxysilane in ethanol medium. The black slurry obtained after the impregnation was finally dried (at 140°) to obtain the magnetic adsorbing bed for the removal of trace amounts (ppm level) of cinnamaldehyde in a commercial grade sample of cinnamyl alcohol.

For analysis, the concentration of cinnamaldehyde in a commercial grade sample of cinnamyl alcohol was checked with mass spectroscopy and was compared with the same sample after adsorption in the prepared adsorbing bed. The amino groups impregnated in the matrix readily underwent reaction with the adsorbed aldehydes and resulted in the formation of Schiff bases thereby reducing the concentration of residual aldehyde contained in the alcohol. The prepared adsorbent was also tested for the removal of heptaldehyde from heptanol and octaldehyde from octanol.

Acknowledgement

This work has been financially supported by the Department of Science & Technology, D.S.T. and C.S.I.R., New Delhi.

References

1. "Healthy Prospects for Nanoceramic Powders" by T. Abraham, International Ceramic Industry, January 2000.
2. R. A. Graham and A. B. Sawaoka, "High Pressure Explosive Processing Ceramics", Trans Tech Publications, Switzerland, 1987.
3. M. N. Rittner, "Beyond the Type : Opportunities and Markets for Nanoparticulate Materials", Business Communications Co., 2001.
4. H. Gleiter, *Nanostructured Mater.*, 1991, **1**, 1.
5. J. Karch, R. Birringer and H. Gleiter, *Nature*, 1987, **330**, 550.
6. D. W. Johnson, *Adv. Ceram.*, 1987, **21**, 3.
7. R. Birringer, *Mater. Sci. Eng. (A)*, 1989, **33**, 117.
8. R. W. Siegel, *MRS Bull.*, 1990, **15**, 60.
9. S. Ram, H. J. Fecht, M. Febry and J. C. Joubert, *Nanostructured Mater.*, 1995, **6**, 470.
10. D. W. Johnson and B. B. Ghate, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, 1985, **15**, 27.
11. S. T. Aruna, Ph.D. Thesis, IISc, Bangalore, India, 1987.
12. "Ultrastructure Processing of Ceramics, Glasses and Composites", eds. E. Matijevic, L. L. Hench and D. R. Ulrich, Wiley, New York, 1984.
13. R. W. Siegel, *Ann. Rev. Mater. Sci.*, 1991, **21**, 559.
14. C. C. Koch, *Nanostructured Mater.*, 1991, **2**, 559.
15. Y. S. Kim and H. M. Jang, *Ceram. Trans.*, 1994, **43**, 123.
16. K. Okaki, H. Maiwa and N. Ichinose, *Ceram. Trans.*, 1994, **43**, 15.
17. J. Frantti and V. J. Lantto, *J. Appl. Phys.*, 1994, **76**, 2139.
18. A. Suyama and A. Kato, *J. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1978, **88**, 212.
19. R. N. Das, A. Pathak and P. Pramanik, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, 1998, **81**, 3357.
20. A. K. Adak, A. Pathak and P. Pramanik, *Br. Ceram. Trans.*, 1999, **98**, 200.
21. A. Sen and P. Pramanik, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.*, 2001, **21**, 745.
22. J. C. Ray, R. K. Pati and P. Pramanik, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.*, 2000, **20**, 1289.
23. R. K. Pati and P. Pramanik, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, 2000, **83**, 1822.
24. P. Klug and L. E. Alexander, "X-ray Diffraction Procedures for Polycrystalline and Amorphous Materials", 2nd. ed., Wiley, New York, 1974.
25. H. Meerwein and R. Schmidt, *Liebigs Ann. Chem.*, 1925, 221.
26. B. Knauer and K. Krohn, *Liebigs Ann. Chem.*, 1995, 677.